

COVID-19 and Distance-Learning of English Language in Cote d'Ivoire: A Case Study through an Analysis of the Situation

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Abstract

The aim of this article was to assess the implementation of distance learning in the teaching-learning of English in Côte d'Ivoire following the onset of the coronavirus disease. Our case study focused on Alassane Ouattara University in Bouaké. Key questions guiding the study as follow: what is the current status of e-learning in English education post-COVID-19? What were the major challenges faced by frontline actors (teachers and students)? Were conditions adequate for these actors to effectively benefit from this new learning paradigm? Did students receive quality education during this period? Did they have the necessary resources to fully engage? What measures should Côte d'Ivoire consider if forced to adopt this new mode of education again? Data were collected using interview guides. Results revealed alarming findings: a lack of digital literacy among key stakeholders, inadequate institutional support and poor teaching quality during COVID-19, and student resource deficiencies. Based on these findings and resilience theory, recommendations for improvement were provided.

Keywords: *Covid-19, Digital tools, E-learning, Resilience.*

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Introduction

With the advent of the coronavirus disease, the world in general, Africa in particular, and especially Côte d'Ivoire found themselves compelled to adopt a new paradigm regarding education. This change was contrary to the usual practices; education now took place remotely rather than face-to-face, where learners and teachers could interact in person. This shift affected all subjects, including the teaching and learning of English as a foreign language. Therefore, the aim of this work was to assess the implementation of distance education in the teaching and learning of English in Côte d'Ivoire following the emergence of COVID-19.

There are several terms and definitions referring to the use of technology in educational systems. Some refer to it as online learning or web-based learning, while others mention web-based training or simply e-learning. In short, it is about facilitating

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learning through information and communication technologies, hence the "e" preceding learning or apprenticeship.

Many researchers have been interested in this method. This is the case in the work of L. Kučirková (2014). According to him, the term e-learning implies that priority is given to learning over teaching. In other words, the learner is at the center of the training process. The American Society for Training and Development (ASTD), on the other hand, considers e-learning to be a type of training that encompasses all technology-based learning. It includes various learning applications and processes, such as computer-based learning, web-based learning, virtual course learning, and digital collaborations. It is learning that occurs through the internet, intranet, satellite broadcasting, audio, video, television, CDs, and many others.

Authors maintain that online learning has not only revolutionized the educational system of institutions but also the understanding of teaching, learning, and especially the experience. This is why they refer to it as the "new ecology of learning" of the 21st century (Kučera & Vydrová 2014; Garrison & Anderson, 2003).

The main questions guiding the study were: What can be learned from the introduction of e-learning in the teaching-learning of English during COVID-19? What were the major challenges faced by frontline actors (teachers and students)? Were the conditions met to effectively benefit from this new training paradigm? Did students receive quality education during this period? Did they have the necessary resources to fully engage? What measures should be taken for Côte d'Ivoire if circumstances or the new world order impose this new way of training again? Our case study focused on Université Alassane Ouattara of Bouaké (UAO).

Theoretical and Methodological Framework

Theoretical Framework

The theory employed to support the study is resilience theory. Resilience in social sciences is generally defined as the ability to recover from negative life experiences and become stronger while overcoming them. According to B. Cyrulnik (2014), resilience occurs when a person undergoes trauma and attempts to overcome it, thereby initiating a process of resilience. Trauma acts as the catalyst for resilience, disrupting the individual's protective bubble and causing confusion. Cyrulnik uses the metaphor of a path to illustrate this concept: "The path of the traumatized is broken. There is a hole, a collapse leading to the precipice." The resilient person, after stopping, charts a new course sideways, integrating the trauma into their personality development. The author emphasizes that resilience development following trauma is never quite the same as it would have been under normal conditions.

It is clear that the COVID-19 pandemic created educational trauma globally, especially in Côte d'Ivoire and specifically at UAO in the teaching and learning of English. Applying resilience theory could aid in addressing such events in the future. Ivorian policymakers could draw inspiration from this theory to regulate distance learning programs in general, particularly in English language education. To achieve this, S. Wolin and S. Wolin (1999) identified seven characteristics essential for facing difficult events: Insight, Independence, Relational Skills, Initiative, Creativity, Humor, and Morality.

Methodological Framework

Data for this study were primarily collected through focus group interviews during Tutorial Sessions. Out of a population of 404 students enrolled during the 2022-2023 academic year in the English department, third year (L3) Tutorial Sessions groups comprised approximately 60 students per session based on attendance lists.

L3 students in 2023 were mostly those who were in their first year (L1) during the 2019-2020 COVID-19 period, hence the choice of this level. According to our hypothesis, their academic year was the most disrupted by the coronavirus due to factors such as their status as newcomers to university life and being unfamiliar with this new environment. Beyond these challenges, they were compelled to face a learning functioning that deviated significantly from past norms.

Grouped into focus groups of about 60 students per session, we tried to collect their learning experiences within the English department during the COVID-19 epidemic.

Beyond learners, some teachers were also associated to the study; they shared their experience of this period. They pointed out their difficulties with, not only the students, but also the teaching tools they had to use. These tools were among others, Microsoft team, Google meet, Zoom US and sometimes WhatsApp. They were 5 in total. Data from these interviews underwent qualitative analysis. The key findings are detailed in the following results.

Note: we have summarized the essence of the different opinions (teachers and learners) in the following table.

Results and Discussion

Questions	Students	Teachers
1) What is your experience of teaching-learning during the Covid-19?	The period of coronavirus has not been easy at all. We hardly studied during that period, because of many reasons. For instance, we did not have enough money to subscribe for internet connection. In addition, some of us did not have smartphones or computers. In one word, we have a poor experience of this time and also the teaching-learning of that time. Even today, we still prefer face-to-face teaching than the distance one.	We cannot say that we have a good experience about this period. We have been forced to do what we could, with the means we had. The goal was to save the academic year. So, we did it.
2) How did you find the teaching supports?	During the courses, we could not hear the teacher sometimes, then we struggled to understand the class. The platform was not working most of time, maybe because of the internet connection.	We have been provided with some digital teaching tools by university authorities. But, we faced many problems with those materials. Sometimes, it was a lack of connection. Sometimes, when we were connected, we could not any students online. Sometimes, most of them were generally connected in the beginning and then disappeared before the end of the session.

Source: Data from the interview guides.

The results revealed an alarming state of the situation

Lack of Digital Literacy Training among Key Stakeholders

Firstly, there was a lack of digital literacy training among some stakeholders. Indeed, it appeared that most students and some teachers faced significant challenges in using the new training software implemented during the COVID-19 period. It should also be noted that some students were completely ignorant about digital tools, while others lacked the means to acquire them.

Absence of Political will from Institutions for Supportive Measures

Secondly, there was an absence of political will from institutions to provide support for creating conducive conditions. The university campus in Bouaké, lacks internet connection. Many students from poor backgrounds could not afford internet access to attend classes; noting the high cost of internet in Côte d'Ivoire. Furthermore, not all regions in the country have internet access, which meant that students who had fled to remote villages to avoid the disease were unable to benefit from online education. All these factors contributed to a decline in the quality of education during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Suggestions

Based on these findings and resilience theory, suggestions have been made to improve the situation in the event of similar challenges in the future:

- **Capacity building for key stakeholders (teachers and students) in digital literacy:** There is a need to enhance the digital literacy skills of teachers and students in education.
- **Support from political and university authorities for easy internet access:** Authorities should support initiatives to ensure easy access to internet data. Providing scholarships to many students so they can purchase connected digital devices is also essential.

Conclusion

COVID-19 had a negative impact on teaching and learning in the English department of almost all Ivorian universities, particularly at UAO. Therefore, university and political authorities should take measures to effectively address such challenges in the future, if they (challenges) were to arise again. They (authorities) could consider applying principles from resilience theory.

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